

Development of a Fast Draping Algorithm Using Multifactorial Simulations of Local Shear

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Introduction and Motivation

- LCM manufacturing processes require draping strategies to be determined for specific mould surfaces
 - It is time consuming, involves lengthy trial and error work in simulation software and on a physical mould
 - Only a fraction of possibilities are probed thus the best strategy rarely is identified
- Decomposing the mould surface into individual geometric features labelled base surfaces can be easily performed in CAD software
 - Base surface are identified as flat, single curvature, double curvature and twist
- A pre-existing database of in-plane shear angles and fibre orientations for parameterized base surfaces is used by the algorithm
 - The algorithm interpolates the data for specific base surfaces linking their results allowing numerous draping scenarios to be probed

Mould Surface CAD Model

CAD Model Base Surfaces

Individual Base Surface	Inputs		Output Shear Angle [°]		
	Start Point	Orientation	Edge	Maximum	Minimum
Double Curvature (Sphere)	Corner	22.5°	1	0	-39.29
			2	21.38	-39.54
			3	21.37	0
Double Curvature (Saddle)	Edge 1	90°	1	-1.50	-41.81
			2	38.9	-41.81
			3	38.9	1.32
			4	1.69	-1.46
Flat	Edge/Centre	Any	No Shear		
Single Curvature	Edge/Centre	Any	No Shear		

Building the Database – The Conical Frustum

- The conical frustum is a multi-parameter tool used to rebuild individual base surfaces in order for draping simulations to be performed
 - Uses vertex coordinates, lengths and radii available in CAD models
- 12 parameter conical frustum can model any base surface
 - Most industrial geometries feature simpler base surfaces hence not all 12 parameters are required
 - Simpler 5 parameter frustum was developed, capable of modeling most cases
- Using draping parameters alongside geometric parameters, simulations are performed yielding results for fibre orientations and in-plane shear angles that are compiled in the database

Conical Frustum Geometric Parameters

R_1	Major axis of ellipse 1
r_1	Minor axis of ellipse 1
R_2	Major axis of ellipse 2
r_2	Minor axis of ellipse 2
L	Distance between ellipses
β_1	Ellipse 1 sectioning angle
β_2	Ellipse 2 sectioning angle
θ_1	Tilt angle ellipse 1
θ_2	Tilt angle ellipse 2
C_R	Major axis connecting radius
c_r	Minor axis connecting radius
α	Rotation/twist angle

Draping Parameters	
P_s	Starting point
O_s	Starting orientation
ω	Angle between warp and weft (pre-existing shear)
S	Fibre spacing

Number of Scenarios and Shear Progression

- The number of scenarios is determined by the number of base surfaces and common edges between base surfaces found on a mould
- From a specified starting position and orientation, each base surface is entered once from a previously probed surface
 - The order in which individuals surface are probed until the full mould is contained is a single scenario
 - As the number of base surface increases, the number of scenarios to probe increases rapidly
- A phenomenon known as shear progression occurs when the fibre orientation and shear varies along a common edge between base surfaces
 - Results in shear propagate into an adjacent surface
 - Database contains results for common edges allowing this phenomenon to be predicted

Changing orientation and shear

Common edge

Conclusion & Future Work

- A first version of the algorithm uses a simplified conical frustum featuring five geometric parameters and four draping parameters
 - Database of in-plane shear and fibre orientations was built using these nine parameters
 - Algorithm interpolates results, linking base surfaces along common edges, and probes numerous draping scenarios to determine the best one – the strategy
- Investigating individual base surfaces allows for more scenarios to be probed systematically, instead of using traditional trial and error
- Future work will involve using the full 12 parameter frustum to expand database and allow more complex base surfaces (twist) to be probed by the algorithm